

The Role Of Political Parties On Election Commission Performance In 2015 Mayor Election Of Ternate City

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Abstract: This research was conducted to evaluate the important role of political parties on electoral commission (KPU) performance in 2015 Ternate city mayor election, North Maluku Province. The research used survey method, with direct observation in population and data collection based on the sampling method. Qualitative data were analyzed statistically. The study used a simple linear model to affect the role of political parties on KPU performance. Data were collected by interview and observation techniques, and tools used were questionnaires. The sequence of data processing as follows; validity and reliability test, classical assumption test, linear regression analysis, determination analysis, and hypothesis test. The result shows that the variable data for all test have very good accuracy and validity, and it is known that the significantly effect of political party on KPU performance in Ternate City is 49.8%. Based on this results, indicates the role of political parties on KPU Performance in Ternate City, related to political communication, political socialization, political recruitment, conflict regulator, recruitment of head of region, people selection, political map, registration period, selection of candidates, selection procedure, introducing platforms, offering policy alternatives, recruiting staff and socializing members.

Index Terms: Political communication, alternative policy, selection procedure.

1 INTRODUCTION

As mandated in the 1945 Constitution of Indonesia and which has undergone 4 (four) changes, that the general election is a manifestation of the people's sovereignty to implement the succession of democratic governance. Implementation of direct, public, free, fair and accountable general elections should be supported by a credible institution. Therefore, the election commission (KPU) should have high integrity, impartiality to one of the election contestants and understand the duties and responsibilities of the KPU, and respect the political rights of the citizens [1]. KPU as the organizer of general elections and as mandated in Law Number 15, 2011 in conducting the general election is committed and guided by the principle of self-reliance, honest, fair, orderly in conducting general election, opened, professional, efficient and effective considering the task of KPU is to hold general election of members of parliament (DPR), members of the regional representative council (DPD), members of the regional parliament (DPRD), as well as the presidential and vice presidential elections held directly by the people. In addition, the duties also carry out the implementation of regional head election (Pemilukada) that is to elect the governor and vice governor and mayor/regent directly, so to carry out the tasks then formed also provincial and regency/City KPU. To carry out these duties the KPU is assisted by the secretary general and the deputy of secretary general (Wasekjen), and all duties are distributed to Bureaus and Inspectorates. While for task implementation of provincial and regency/city KPU assisted by the secretariat of provincial regency/city.

Therefore, the KPU general secretary as a government agency shall prepare performance reports (LAKIP) as mandated in presidential instruction No. 7 of 1999 on performance accountability of government institutions and regulation of the minister of administrative reform and state apparatus No. 29 Year 2010 concerning guidelines for formulating performance and performance accountability report government agencies report the successful implementation accountability of organization's mission in achieving the target set [2]. Democracy is the government by and for the people. Democracy is a form or system of government in which all people intervene in giving participation and aspiration in public policy formulation through people's representatives or government mediation. The democratic system is regarded as the best and ideal form of government because it is seen as a system that upholds people's freedom and promotes equality. Democracy can also be interpreted as an idea or a worldview that prioritizes equality of rights, duties, and equal treatment for all citizens. The idea of direct democracy in selecting political leaders from the point of view of anti-corruption in order to avoid buying and selling votes in parliament, in order to increase legitimacy and public accountability. Since the era of the old order, the new order, until the order of reform before the enactment of Law No. 32 of 2004, almost every election of regional head always colored with money politics in the DPRD [3]. General election is a means of people sovereignty implementation to held directly, publicly, freely, secretly, honestly and fairly in Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the Constitution. Election is one instruments of democracy that involve quality participation of society in realizing its aspirations channeled through the political parties. Elections have meaning and significance as a means of manifesting the people sovereignty in order to produce Indonesian government democratic, because the characteristic of a democratic country is the existence of an election [4]. The general elections shall be held once every five years, as set out in Article 22E Paragraph (1) of Indonesian Constitution. Election which is one form of community involvement in the political process, is also a means for the community to participate in determining the figure and direction of state or regional leadership within a certain period. When democracy gets widespread attention

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from the world community, democratic elections are an essential prerequisite for the establishment of a country's leadership. Elections have a role to produce leadership that is really close to the people will and is one of the legitimate means of obtaining power legitimacy based on the constitution. The political parties position in the election is very strategic. This is in accordance with Law No. 32 of 2004 and Government Regulation No. 6 of 2005, all candidates who are entitled to advance in battle must be nominated certain political parties. In fact, candidates for eligible regional heads must go through a political party or coalition of political parties with 15% of seats in the parliament or vote in legislative elections. In the implementation of election that can happen otherwise, the effect and role of political parties that should be able to dominate the implementation of regional election (Pilkada), was very minimal. It turns out that political parties regarded as a political machine cannot be moved to win a candidate, because his strength is very limited. If a candidate nominated for more than one political party then wins in the election, it is more due to figures factor and not caused by support of political parties. But the role of decisive still great, especially as pacemaker for someone to be able as a candidate. Based on the above description, it is necessary to evaluate the role of political parties on the KPU performance in 2015 mayor election of Ternate North Maluku, so that the quality of the upcoming general elections is better.

2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses survey method, where the observation is done directly on large or small population but the data collection by sampling from the population. The qualitative data then analyzed using statistical method. Relationship between variables using associative model to know as the variables studied it will explain the object under study through the data collected. The role of political parties in relation to KPU performance uses simple linear analysis. A political party is a national organization and is formed by a group of Indonesian citizens voluntarily on the basis of equality and ideals to fight and defend the political interests of members, society, nation and state, and to maintain the unity of Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. Political parties are scores obtained by respondents in answering the questionnaire of 15 items in a structure and measurement parameters using the Likert scale with a score of 1 to 5 (positive statements) and 5 to 1 (negative statements). The variables indicators are political communication, political socialization, political recruitment, conflict regulator, mayor recruitment, people selection, political map, registration period, candidate selection, selection procedure, aggregating interests, introducing platforms, offering policy alternatives, staff and members of the community. The KPU performance is an ability that has the only trustworthy evidence to conclude whether an organization, unit or employee is successful or failing, achieving or not. To assess a performance requires an overall understanding. There are three kinds of performance goals that are known, which is organizational performance, unit performance and KPU performance. Performance of KPU is the score obtained by respondents in answering the questionnaire of 15 items in a structured and measurement parameters using Likert scale with a score of 1 to 5 (positive statement) and 5 to 1 (negative statements). The indicators of this variable are preparing someone, improving conditions, assigning tasks, basics, comparators, determinants,

successes, loyalty, crafts, abilities, development, relationships, carrying out tasks, accountability and feedback. The population in this study consists of political parties, bureaucracy (Echelon II, III & IV), mayor candidates, KPU, candidates teams and 731 people. The sample of this research is done by stratified proportional random sampling technique, that is random sampling in population which have been grouped (population) based on group stratum from population in Ternate City of North Maluku Province. This technique is used when the population has members or elements that are not homogeneous and stratified proportionately. Data were collected through questionnaires, interviews and observations, while the tools used in data collection were questionnaires [5]. Furthermore, tested the validity and reliability, assumption testing, statistical analysis, determination analysis, hypothesis testing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Object of Research

The research was conducted in Ternate mayor election on 2015. Ternate city is an archipelago town with an area of 547,736 km², covering 8 islands. Topography of Ternate is dominated by mountainous and hilly terrain, is a volcanic and atoll island is composed of Rogusal and Rensika soil types. Topographic variation between 0-700 m above sea level. Ternate is heavily affected by the ocean climate and has two seasons are often interspersed with twice the transition period in each year [6]. Sultan Babullah Airport is a means of air transportation in Ternate City. Some airlines that serve this route include Garuda Indonesia, Sriwijaya Air, Batavia Air, Wings Air (Lion Air Group), Merpati Airlines, Express Air and Trigana Air. Flights via Makassar, Manado and Sorong. The city also has A. Yani sea port with a cruise line that passes *Pelni* ship twice per week. Map of research location as in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research location

Election Commission (KPU) of Ternate City

The law on elections has established that the KPU is a national, permanent and independent institution. In addition to the rights and obligations as stipulated in provisions of legislation, the KPU is also obliged; 1) implement and comply

with state laws and regulations; 2) carry out duties honestly and fairly; 3) respect the principle of openness and the importance of providing appropriate, honest, and accountable information to the public; 4) carry out the tasks established under the Act; 5) ensure that every election participant, including political parties, candidates for legislative members and voters, is treated equitably and equitably; 6) carries out coordinated duties among members or with relevant agencies; and 7) support the monitoring of elections to proceed effectively and efficiently [6].

Description of Political Parties Variable Data

The results of questionnaires distribution for political party variable data showed that the lowest score was 2.87 and the highest score was 4.87. Thus, the lowest and highest scores were obtained, then the range of scores was 2.00. The numbers after analyzing resulted in an average score (mean) of 4.0258, variance of 0.120, and standard deviation of 0.34619. If presented in tabular form, then the frequency distribution of political party variable scores as in Table 1. Based on Table 1, it can be interpreted that political parties are political organizations that can act as aspirations channels of public, of which 92.4% of respondents agree with the results. Political parties become the liaison between ruler and power. The existence of a political party allows the people to be directly involved in the process of organizing the state by placing their representatives through political parties. In general, political parties are said to be a group with the same goals and ideals, which seek to gain power through elections. The main objective of a political party is to control the government so that they can more freely execute their desires and make a profit. Political parties are different from movements. A movement usually uses politics to make a change to an existing order in society, and some even want to create an entirely new social order. Political parties have a broader purpose than a change, political parties also participate in his election in the election. Political parties are also different from the pressure group or better known as the inters group. The interest group only aims to fight for a particular interest by influencing the decision maker. Interest groups are usually outside the political party, coming from groups within the community. From the analysis results obtained the frequency distribution of political party variables such as Figure 2.

Figure 2. Frequency distribution of political party variable score

Table 1.: Frequency Distribution of Political Parties Variables

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2.87	1	.2	.2
	3.13	2	.4	.7
	3.20	5	1.1	1.7
	3.33	8	1.7	3.5
	3.40	8	1.7	5.2
	3.47	11	2.4	7.6
	3.53	15	3.3	10.9
	3.60	11	2.4	13.3
	3.67	16	3.5	16.7
	3.73	22	4.8	21.5
	3.80	21	4.6	26.1
	3.87	33	7.2	33.3
	3.93	32	7.0	40.2
	4.00	49	10.7	50.9
	4.07	49	10.7	61.5
	4.13	27	5.9	67.4
	4.20	23	5.0	72.4
	4.27	29	6.3	78.7
	4.33	17	3.7	82.4
	4.40	17	3.7	86.1
	4.47	27	5.9	92.0
	4.53	9	2.0	93.9
	4.60	11	2.4	96.3
	4.67	9	2.0	98.3
	4.73	2	.4	98.7
	4.80	4	.9	99.6
	4.87	2	.4	100.0
Total	460	100.0	100.0	

Based on Figure 2, it is seen that 878 or 12.72% of respondents are in average group, respondents 291 or 4.22% are below the average and 5,731 respondents or 83.06% above the average. Thus, the questionnaire can be used as a tool for measuring research. From these statements, it can be said that political parties are included in very good category. This can be seen from 5,731 or 83,06% respondents appreciate statement with very good response to political party in Ternate City. Furthermore, perceptions of respondents to the political party variables dimensions can be seen in Figure 3-5.

Figure 3. Perception of respondents on political party purpose dimension

Figure 4. Perceptions of respondents on direct mayor election dimension

Figure 5. Perceptions of respondents on democratization purpose dimension

The dimension of political party purpose consists of four indicators, that is communication, socialization, recruitment, and conflict regulator. Based on Figure 3, it is known that 215 or 11.68% of respondents are in average group, 79 respondents or 4.3% are below the average and 1,546 respondents or 84.02% above the average. From the description, it can be said that the purpose of political parties included in very well category. This can be seen from 1,546 or 84.02% respondents appreciate the statement with very good response to political party purpose in Ternate City. The direct mayor election dimension consists of six indicators, which is the recruitment of mayor, people selection, political map, registration period, candidate selection, and procedure. Based on Figure 4, there is 118 respondents or 4.28% were below the average and 2,285 respondents or 82.79% above the average, it can be concluded that the direct election dimension is very good category. This can be seen from 2,285 or 82.79% of respondents appreciating the statement with very good response to direct elections in Ternate City. The third dimension of the political party variables consists of five indicators, that is aggregate interests, introduce platforms, offer policy alternatives, recruit staff, and socialize members. From the calculation of Figure 5 above, it is seen that 306 or 13.31% of respondents are in the average group, 94 respondents or 4.08% are below the average and 1,900

respondents or 82.61% above average. From the above information, it can be concluded that the dimension of democratization function is included in either category. It can be seen from about 1,900 or 82,61% respondents appreciate statement with good response to democratization purpose in Ternate City. From the analysis, it is known that from those three dimensions which have the significantly effect in determining political party is the purpose dimension of 84,02%.

Reliability, Validity, and Multicollinearity Test

Reliability and validity test of raw data was conducted to check the consistency of measuring tool and validity of each questionnaire. To obtain accurate calculation results, the calculation process using computer program SPSS. The result of reliability and validation test toward community participation variable and KPU performance showed good reliability level with reliability coefficient more than 0,6, while validity test result on both variable showed very valid. The multicollinearity test is performed to find out whether there is collinearity or not among independent variables. The method used is to calculate tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). From the calculation of computer with SPSS program obtained tolerance value for each stage of research. The results of this test show an excellent level of suitability.

The Role of Political Parties on KPU Performance

As mentioned in Article 65 paragraph (3) of Indonesian Law No. 32/2004, the implementation stage of KPU performance shall include: (a) register of voters register, (b) registration and determination of prospective candidate pair, (c) campaign, (d) voting, (e) vote counting and (f) determination of candidate pair. Similarly, the presence of political party in Ternate City, as a pillar for democratic system upholding of political parties also has a substantial role and contribution to the implementation and smoothness of KPU performance process as set forth in Article 65 paragraph (3) Law Number 32/2004. Public education, the best cadres competition, to evaluation of elections, all that cannot be separated from the portrait of political parties in Ternate City. The role of political parties in Ternate City on KPU performance can be explained as follows, namely; the prospecting process of candidates as mandated by Law No. 32/2004 article 59 paragraph (1), that participants of election proposed in pairs by the political parties or coalition of political parties. Thus, political parties have been given full authority as a bearer for each candidate pair who will onwards to compete in election. So that, there is no other option for party cadres not to use political parties as the main requirement to onwards as a election. So that a political party as a trusted actor in filtering prospective candidates from each pair, must have a selective internal party mechanism in the selection of prospective candidates. Furthermore, based on all variable analysis and test data to determine the accuracy and validity, it can be explained the important role of political parties on KPU performance. Political parties participation in giving color during the elections in Ternate City, has implications for election implementation of the best mayor.

a. Positive Implications

Positive implication is a form of effect that gives the impact of progress, smoothness for election implementation in Ternate City from existence of political party role. Positive implications include; 1) as stipulated in Law No.32/2004 article 59 paragraph (1). Based on the positive assumption of political

party role on election implementation in Ternate City, it can be explained that the role of political party, the candidate pairs can compete in the fight for position as mayor. Thus, in addition to the entrance of the candidate pair can also be a bearer for each candidate to be easy in fulfilling all requirements as candidate that has been established law; 2) with the party's authority granted by Law, especially regarding the KPU performance, the party must strive to establish an internal party mechanism in recruiting its best cadres or local candidate to be promoted as mayor candidates. So, for the voters, with the existence mechanism of political parties, the people have been provided by the best mayor candidates as a result of qualification of each political party; 3) the existing party, also acting as an extension of KPU Ternate City as the organizer of the election. In this case, the party usually participates in socializing voting procedures to party members and the public in general, so that the public will be informed how to follow good and correct electoral procedures. In addition, the party that carries the candidates in mayor election also seeks to socialize (introduce) the candidate pair through the media campaign to be better known to the public; 4) the party also functions as a conflict regulator, especially among the supporters of each candidate. In the election process in Ternate City, the political party that carries the candidate pair of mayor election, has emphasized to the candidate pairs, to apply the principle of peaceful campaign in every opportunity given by Ternate City KPU. This thing is able to encourage safe and smooth condition in the KPU performance in Ternate City; 5) political parties are also entitled to oversee the election process up to the final vote counting process by sending some cadres as witnesses or monitors in the election process. So that with the control mechanism of each party (KPU, party or candidate pair, and public), various fraud or violation can be reduced as much as possible.

b. Negative Implications

In addition to the positive implications and the role of political parties, the existence of political party on KPU performance in Ternate City also has negative implications, namely; 1) in recruiting candidates for mayor election, political parties always rely on the intervention of party central board; 2) when the campaign of each candidate pair, the party is often unable to manage its mass in an orderly and secure manner. So that arises are the violations in traffic, disrupt public peace, and other violations that should not have occurred during the campaign period. The purpose of political party formation is to fight and defend the political interests of members, public, nation and state, and maintaining the state integrity. In addition, political parties as a pillar of democracy need to be organized and refined by being directed to two main things, namely; 1) establishing the attitude and behavior of patterned or systemic political parties so as to form a political culture that supports the basic principles of democratic system. This is demonstrated by the attitude and behavior of political parties that have adequate selection and recruitment systems and developing strong cadre and political leadership systems; 2) maximize the political parties function both to the state and to the people through political education and cadre, and effective political recruitment to produce cadres of candidate leaders who have the ability in politics. Political party are groups of people who are organized in a stable manner in order to seize or retain government control of their party's leaders, and on the basis of this satisfaction gives party members an ideal and

material benefit. Political parties are a group of rather organized citizens, who act as political unity, who by power utilization electing, aim at government mastering and implementing their general policies [8]. Furthermore, the political parties are an articulate organization composed of politically active actors in the society, those who focus their attention on mastering the power of government and those competing for people support and some other groups who have different views [9]. Thus, political parties are the great intermediaries that connect social forces and ideologies with official governmental institutions and which relate them to political action within a broader political society. From the above opinion, political parties are defined as an organized group whose members have the same values and ideals oriented to gain power and seize political sovereignty through the acquired power to carry out their policies. The articulation of opinions and attitudes from various groups that are more or less related to the same thing are combined into a merger of interests which in a political system is an input to the ruling government. Conversely, if the articulation of opinions and attitudes are not well accumulated then that will arise is a competition of uncontrolled interests and will eventually lead to anarchy. In other words, political parties are in charge of disorderly public will.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The study on the role of political parties on KPU performance in Ternate City mayor election was conducted with methods and tests of accuracy and excellent data validity. Based on this result, it is concluded that the effect of political party on KPU performance in Ternate City is 49.8%. This indicates the importance of political parties on KPU Performance in Ternate City, related to political communication, political socialization, political recruitment, conflict regulator, mayor recruitment, people selection, political map, registration period, candidates selection, selection procedure, introducing platforms, offering policy alternatives, recruiting staff and socializing members.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Siti Zuhro, et al., (2009), *Local Democracy: Changes and Continuity of Local Political Cultural Values in East Java, West Sumatra, South Sulawesi and Bali*, Yogyakarta: Waves.
- [2] Rozali Abdullah, (2005), *Implementation of Regional Autonomy Through Direct Elections*, Rajawali Pers, Jakarta.
- [3] Koswara, Kertapradja, (2000), *Regional Autonomy: For Democracy & Independence of the People*, Jakarta: PT. Candi Cipta Paramuda.
- [4] Samsul Wahidin, (2008), *Supervising the Regional Head Election*, Yogyakarta, Pustaka Pelajar.
- [5] Likert, R. (1932). A Technique for the Measurement of Attitudes, *Archives of Psychology*, 140, 1-55.
- [6] Abdul Halil Hi. Ibrahim, (2017), Effect of Public Participation to Improve the Election Commission (KPU) Performance in Ternate City Major Election, *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 7 (1), pp. 1-7.

- [7] Carl J. Friedrich, (2009), Understanding Constitutionalism as a Political System, The European Legacy Journal, 14 (3), 283-300.
- [8] Roger H. Soltau, (1961), An Introduction to Politics, Longmans, Green and Company.
- [9] Neumann, Sigmund. 2000, Modern Political Parties, Comparative Politics, London, The Free Press Of Glencoe.